

EU MAP webinar: Towards a Roadmap for Vibrant Mountain Economies

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

8 May 2024

The fourth EU Multi-Actor Platform (EU MAP) webinar [“Towards a Roadmap for Vibrant Mountain Economies”](#) was held on May 8th, 2024, only a few weeks before the European Parliament’s elections and several months ahead of the next European Commission’s proposal for the post-2027 EU agenda.

This online event set a **milestone for discussing the role of mountains in the post-2027 EU political agenda**. The specific objectives of the meeting were to:

- Present the MOVING’s Strategic Options and Policy Roadmap;
- Provide an overview of the current discussions concerning post-2027 policy development, in particular the ones related to mountain and territorial development;
- Discuss how MOVING’s Strategic Options and Policy Roadmap can be supported within the post-2027 EU policies.

Moderated by Carla Lostrangio, Rural and Territorial Expert at AEIDL on behalf of the [MOVING project](#) and supported by the [EU Local Innovation Forum \(ELIF\)](#), the event brought together experts from the **European Commission, European Parliament, European Committee of the Regions** and pan European network experts (**CEMR and Euromontana**). The discussion examined how the already ongoing post-2027 EU policy discussions can inform the EU policy roadmap for sustainable mountain development that MOVING is preparing for its [Final Conference](#) (13-14 June, Brussels).

Key reports on the current status and future perspectives of rural areas were used to set the frame for the discussion, including the progress report of the [EU’s Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas](#), the [9th Cohesion Report](#) and the [High-Level Report on the Future of the Cohesion Policy](#). Hence, the MOVING’s [30 Strategic Options](#) for enhancing mountain sustainability and its **Policy Roadmap** were presented.

ORGANISER:

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ONLINE

81 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

24 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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The Policy Roadmap was commented on in a **final round table**, which focused on how future policies should be supporting Europe's mountains. In this round table, speakers underscored the tendency of policies to operate in isolation, highlighting the value of integrated building blocks with a cross-cutting nature and a mixed approach. They found the inclusion of infrastructure support and the enhancement of governance to be particularly compelling.

Final recommendations called on the need to adopt a cross-

cutting and holistic approach when targeting mountains; reconsider the distribution of funds between urban and rural areas; address existing gaps in funding priorities and distribution of competences; strengthen national policymaking and good practices' sharing related to mountains. The MOVING project will integrate the outputs of the discussion in its Policy Roadmap and Recommendations, that will be presented at the **MOVING Final Conference** (13-14 June 2024, Brussels) before they are shared with European institutions.

The MOVING Project: An Overview

María del Mar DELGADO

MOVING Coordinator, University of Cordoba

Mar Delgado, Full Professor at the University of Córdoba and MOVING coordinator, initiated her presentation by introducing the project to the participants, conveying the objective of the project. She underscored the pivotal role of mountains and the imperative to recognize and maintain their essential value which provides socio-economic and environmental benefits to high and lowland communities. Mar also reflected on the diversity of mountain areas and the need to tailor policies and measures to reflect the specificities and characteristics of these regions across various geographical levels.

**“Our point of departure: (un)valued mountains”,
Mar Delgado**

Hence, Mar proceeded to outline the **main results** that have been obtained in the last four years of project development: the [Conceptual Analytical Framework](#), the [MOVING Value Chains' Inventory](#), findings from [participatory analyses of land use system vulnerability](#), a [Value Chain cross-comparison and benchmarking report](#), and the [Participatory multilevel foresight](#).

The work focused on mountain value chains, has been structured to first understand their diversity, followed by analysing them to ascertain their potential, and finally defining perspectives for their upgrade. Additionally, the project has formulated the **Policy Roadmap**, the focal point of this webinar, and fostered the establishment of a [Community of Practice](#) (23 Regional Multi-Actor Platforms and 1 EU-level Multi-Actor Platform) throughout its lifetime.

As Mar recalled in the conclusive part of her intervention, MOVING's legacy stands into the listening to over **1.000 mountain stakeholders**, validation of scientific results with local knowledge and going beyond 'case-by-case approach' while preserving uniqueness. She emphasized the need to acknowledge territorial mountain diversity as a crucial asset for Europe and create **a new narrative on mountains**, moving from areas with natural constraints to regions with unique traits that create opportunities. More granular data, multi-level support and mixed policy interventions are examples of measures that should be promoted to unlock the power of mountain Value Chains.

MOVING Community of Practice

Figure 1. MOVING's Results over the project's lifetime. Source: Mar Delgado's presentation.

POST-2027 POLICY DISCUSSION

The long-term vision for rural areas: key achievements & ways forward

Silvia NANNI, DG AGRI - European Commission

Silvia Nanni, Policy Officer at DG AGRI – European Commission, began her presentation by referring to the relevance of the Commission's support for rural areas and to the recent report published on 27 March 2024 on the "[Long-term vision for the EU's rural areas: key achievements and ways forward](#)".

The report provides **looks back at 30 months of implementation** of the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, and its contribution to rural development along its four pillars (Stronger, Connected, Resilient and Prosperous Rural Areas), and a **look forward** towards the consolidation of the EU Rural Action Plan and Rural Pact.

On policies contributing to rural areas, Silvia also referred in her presentation to the latest reports on the CAP ([September](#) and [November 2023](#)) and [Cohesion Policy](#).

She continued illustrating the **24 thematic actions** of the EU Rural Action Plans and key milestones for the four action areas and the **6 cross-cutting actions** considered horizontal such as

better statistics, a methodology to define functional rural areas, accessibility to the Rural Observatory and Toolkit on rural funds, the mechanism for the Rural proofing included to be considered in the Better regulation guidelines and toolbox and the operation of the Rural Pact that is directly linked to the governance.

Silvia concluded with an emphasis on **future opportunities for stakeholders to engage in the EU post-2027 EU policy debate** and the **eleven reflective questions** advanced by the European Commission to continue shaping their work on rural areas such as: what are the main challenges arising from depopulation, ongoing transitions and structural changes, how to address them and how to increase financial support and improve access to support. Also, how to improve the monitoring and evaluation of the resources of the different EU funds and programmes, ensure institutional, governance and integrated support to rural areas and improve the availability of policy-relevant rural statistics and data.

Post-2027 Territorial Development in Europe: What is at stake? Where do we stand?

Balazs SZECHY, European Parliament Research Service

Balazs Szechy, European Parliament Research Service, focused his presentation on the recent [9th Cohesion report](#) published on 27 March, presenting an assessment of the state of social, economic and territorial cohesion in the European Union. As he underlined, this report was accepted by almost all members of the European Parliament, so it is understood that there is a certain consensus in the institution with regard to its analysis.

In this report, **Chapter 3.5** includes an assessment of "**Regions with Specific Geographic Features**" including mountains. As the report points out, geographical specificities pose additional challenges on mountain regions such as the difficult accessibility, low service provision, high infrastructure costs and limited availability of arable land. On the other side, mountains can capitalize on their natural resources, forest land and tourism potential.

The COVID-19 period (2020 and 2021) had a stronger negative impact on mountain areas in terms of GDP growth rate per person. The report illustrates that mountains are characterized by **lower employment rate** and **lower share of the population in tertiary education** than the than the EU-27 average.

Balazs pointed out the role of [European Parliament Rural, Mountainous and Remote Areas \(RUMRA\)](#) Intergroup to jointly put stakeholders from rural and mountain areas. This Intergroup promotes integrated development for European territories in all their diversity. The Intergroup enables exchanges on innovative ways to create vibrant and attractive rural communities.

He shared his **key messages** for the future of the European

Parliament's implementation report over the period 2014-2020 (vid the recent [Novakov REGI Report](#)), as follows:

- Increase the overall cohesion budget and allocate special resources to disadvantaged regions.
- Ensure all regions are eligible for cohesion funding and receive targeted assistance.
- Strengthen the principle of shared management and simplify the cohesion structure.
- Divide cohesion post-2027 into content and financial parts.
- Implement cohesion based on performance metrics.
- Uphold the "do no harm to cohesion" principle, preventing policies from exacerbating regional disparities.
- Consider additional factors beyond GDP when determining support levels.
- Allocate special funds for border regions in the cohesion budget.
- Address challenges posed by green, digital, and industrial transitions, support sustainable mobility, energy efficiency, and disaster resilience.
- Evaluate the impact of enlargement on cohesion policy before the new programming period.

Balazs concluded highlighting that the debate on the future of cohesion after 2027 is already alive and kicking. The Platform [What Europe does for me \(europa.eu\)](#) is an interactive and multilingual website that gives access to thousands of easy-to-read, one-page notes providing examples of the difference that the EU can make to people's lives.

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING's RESULTS

Strategic Options for Vibrant Mountain Economies

Dominique Barjolle, Origin for Sustainability

Dominique Barjolle, Director of Origin for Sustainability, led the MOVING's work on regional and European foresight. She began her intervention by presenting the **essential Functions of Mountains**: (i) Conservation and preservation of natural resources; (ii) Geostrategy; (iii) Production and Heritage and (iv) Recreation and Well-being. These functions are **endangered** by current threats, in particular climate change, population loss and market disruptions are endangering mountains' essential functions. It is therefore necessary to claim solid mountain policies that make them more visible and more visible.

In this perspective, they identified four long-term forces (markets, climate change, tourism dynamics, demography) and used them

to run **22 regional foresight exercises and 1 European foresight exercise**. The goal of these exercises was to choose a desirable future scenario for mountains (named as 'archetypes') and select some Strategic Options to enable it.

Four archetypes emerged from the MOVING exercises: i) Economic Driven; ii) Nature Driven, iii) Niche and Diversification Driven, iv) Knowledge and Innovation Driven. Archetypes can be described as the lens people put on to see the future: through the lens of Economy, through the lens of Nature, and so on. The **most common thread or archetype** MOVING found through its cases studies was the economics-driven vision.

Figure 2. MOVING four archetypes

Hence, Dominique introduced the MOVING **Strategic Options**, i.e. **solutions funded through various mechanisms to address mountain specific challenges**, and the methodology used for their definition. As she explained, Strategic Options have been discussed with the 23 regional Multi-Actor Platforms' (MAPs) coordinators of the project and EU experts. An attempt was made to first look at the common grand challenges of the regions and the key variables that stakeholders can influence are the same in all regions. Strategic options across Europe could better address specific challenges in the mountains. They can be limited or broad in scope, targeting

different sectors or activities. They can also be **replicated** elsewhere **with adjustments**, supported by national or European mechanisms.

Dominique concluded with a reflection about how shifting from Strategic Options to policy responses recognizing the absence of a one-size-fits-all policy mix for addressing all mountain needs. Also, she defended that policies should improve the framework for supporting the development and implementation of Strategic Options.

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING's RESULTS

MOVING Policy Roadmap

Mark Redman, Highclere Consulting

Mark Redman, Highclere Consulting and lead partner on policy analysis and recommendations in the project, began by stating that there is an urgent need for an **'institutional transformation'** to sustain the ecological and social systems of our mountains. In this respect, **Policy Roadmap** can be used as a strategic tool for **structuring, planning and communicating proposed actions and initiatives**, including policy recommendations.

Policy Roadmap provides flexibility to support various forms of transformation and other development processes especially useful for guiding/facilitating transformations affecting multiple policy areas. It also provides space to engage local actors and stakeholders in a dynamic framework for realising strategic visions and options for the future.

The **MOVING Policy Roadmap** aims at synthesizing, structuring, and communication the project's findings in a Policy Context. In particular, it produces a compelling narrative, helps define practical guidance of currently available policy instruments (2021-2027) and delivers relevant recommendations for longer-term term improvements in future policies (to 2050).

Mark pointed out that strong **local governance** can make constructive differences in the well-being of local residents. Mechanisms to strengthen mountain governance remain elusive but benefit from approaches that fit local contexts while building

equitable and creative collaborations among diverse, supportive actors within and beyond mountain communities.

The multi-faceted components of the MOVING Policy Roadmap are built upon the project's Conceptual Analytical Framework. In constructing the MOVING policy roadmap, and knowing the limited scope of existing policies, we have used **Policy Building Blocks** ('enabling blocks') that represent clusters of interventions, structures, processes and working methods to enhance the contribution of mountain product value chains to sustainable and resilient mountain areas.

These are: i) Growing Skills, Knowledge & Innovation; ii) Fostering Collaboration & Networking, iii) Balancing Ecology & Society; iv) Preparing & Adapting for Change; v) Sustaining the Use of Local Assets; vi) Ensuring Mountain Livelihoods; vii) Implementing Better Governance & Regulation. The MOVING Policy Building blocks are inspired by other examples, such as from OECD or the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas.

Policy Building Blocks provide the basis for a first level of **policy mixing** and can be assembled in different ways in response to the needs associated with specific challenges and/or opportunities. For example, through the identification of local/regional Transition/Transformation Pathways (Foresight Archetypes).

Figure 3. MOVING Policy Building Blocks for the Policy Roadmap. Source: Mark Redman's presentation.

ROUND TABLE

Feedback on MOVING Policy Roadmap

Moderated by **Carla Lostrangio**, European Association for Innovation in Local Development

Guillaume Corradino
Euromontana

Michael Schmitz
Council of European
Municipalities and Regions

Klaus Boele
CoR NAT Commission

The roundtable discussion began with reflections on the proposed MOVING Policy Roadmap and whether there are elements that could still be included. **Klaus Boele**, EU Committee of the Regions, emphasized (on the back of the recent [Boc-Cordeiro Opinion](#) and the draft [Gomes Opinions](#), inter alia) the significance of translating project outcomes and outputs beyond mere project results, noting their potential to impact processes across various scales and influence decision-making among different stakeholders. The suggestion was made to refine the language used in the roadmap to closely align with the current policy agenda, facilitating advocacy efforts. This proposition garnered support from **Michael Schmitz**, Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR).

Furthermore, roundtable members underscored the tendency of policies to operate in isolation, highlighting the value of integrated building blocks with a **cross-cutting nature** and a **mixed approach**. Specifically, they found the inclusion of infrastructure support and the enhancement of governance to be particularly compelling (as expressed by all roundtable participants).

Carla Lostrangio asked the panellists their perception on **how policies have addressed the specificities of mountains over the past decades**, and whether they overlooked some interventions for their sustainability. **Guillaume Corradino**, Euromontana, commented that mountains experienced a lack of recognition in the past. At the same time, he said to understand this failure because mountains are complex socio-eco-environmental systems and this complexity cannot be addressed easily and without specific measures. Hence the importance of continuing to strengthen research with projects such as this one and to continue advancing in the territorial based approach.

Furthermore, Carla Lostrangio asked how to acknowledge and

reward the **non-economic benefits of mountains**, such as social outcomes and other ecosystem services, in the post-2027 EU policies. Klaus Boele stressed the need to have a cross-cutting approach between the different existing policies. Michael stresses the importance of reviewing the distribution of funds between urban and rural areas. It also points out that there is still a gap in funding priorities and at the level of distribution of competences. The local level, not only governments but also other actors in the local environment, are overwhelmed by bureaucratic burdens and lack of capacity. It is important to strengthen the cohesion principle in the sense of capacity building.

Carla Lostrangio launched the final question: "Going beyond the EU's Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, in your opinion, where should key EU policies, in particular Cohesion Policy and Common Agricultural Policy, direct their efforts to support mountain areas in the **post-2027 period?**".

Klaus Boele underscored the need to consider mobility and cross-border cooperation as strategic priorities. Guillaume particularly commended the monitoring of mountain areas and policy actions targeted to these regions. He also added on the importance to design tailored and place-based policies not only at European level but also at national level, making sure that Member States continue sharing good practices among each other. Michael reflected on the decentralisation of Cohesion Policy and the risk of minimising the capacity to support infrastructure through CAP rural development interventions. Also, the level of co-financing is important to rethink it in order to address the needs and what level of NUT can be the recipient of funds if we want to reach specific needs of mountain areas and not only rural areas.

ABOUT ELIF

The European Local Innovation Forum (ELIF)

European Association for Innovation in Local Development

The event was supported by the [European Local Innovation Forum \(ELIF\)](#), a platform counting approximately 2,000 stakeholders engaged in local innovation across 27 EU countries and 12 non-EU countries. Launched in November 2022, the forum is intended to exchange practices and ideas targeted to promote innovation and local development.

It consists of two Thematic Communities facilitated by the European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL), namely the Territorial Development Community and the Social Innovation Community. Linking the last MOVING MAP Meeting and ELIF made sense given that some of the final results of MOVING are directly relevant and can be utilised by the wide ELIF community and likewise ELIF open ended and virtual setting is a further avenue where MOVING partners can continue engaging in the topics covered throughout the life of the project beyond the project's end this summer.

In 2024, several ELIF working meetings and other activities have been planned to continue exchanging and getting inspired on local innovation.

Do you want to know more about the project and the community? Find more information, [here](#).
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